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Is wine price a guarantee for its healthful properties?

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Wine phenolics influence the colour, bouquet, astringency, and bitterness of the wine, and represent chemotaxonomic markers for distinguishing different grape varieties ¹. Besides contributing to the quality of wine by affecting the organoleptic properties, phenolic compounds are also mainly responsible for the health benefits associated with wine, thanks to their strong antioxidant activity ². In this study a quality assessment was made by comparing the market price, biological activity and phenolic content of six commercially available Cabernet Sauvignon wines from the region of Fruška Gora, Serbia. Wines were divided into two groups based on the price range - lower (manufacturers: Podrum Petrović, MK Kosović, Dulka) and higher (manufacturers: Bajilo, Mrđanin, Živanović) priced products. The antioxidant potential of the samples was determined through the scavenging of diphenylpicrylhydrazyl and nitric oxide radicals, and Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power assay (FRAP), while the neuroprotective effect was estimated through a potential inhibition of acetylcholinesterase. Also, total phenolic and flavonoid contents of Cabernet Sauvignon wines were determined spectrophotometrically. Generally, two out of three higher priced wines did exert a better biological activity and higher phenolic and flavonoid content, compared with lower priced products, with Cabernet Sauvignon Živanović being the most representative sample. However, Cabernet Sauvignon Podrum Petrović did not only express the best activity amongst the lower priced wines, it also proved to be the most active sample to scavenge nitric oxide, with the highest flavonoid content compared to all the tested wines. Novel data on commercial Cabernet Sauvignon wines from Fruška Gora presented here show a good correlation between the biological activity and the total phenolic and flavonoid content of the samples, suggesting that these compounds do influence the health benefits of wine and contribute to its quality. However, a clear correlation between the price and biological activity was not observed.

Acknowledgements

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